

I GENDER EQUALITY PLAN

2021- 2023

**of the Agencia Estatal de Investigación
(State Research Agency of Spain)
for R&D&I funding activities**

AEI Strategic Group on Gender Equality

January 2021

1.- INTRODUCTION

The *Agencia Estatal de Investigación* (AEI) (State Research Agency of Spain) established its own Strategic Group on Gender Equality (GEI-AEI) in November 2018, to systematise and boost the gender equality strategies and measures committed to in the Roadmap for the development of the ERA in Spain 2016-2020, and on which the Agency had made some progress in recent years. The H2020 SUPERA project, coordinated by Spain, created a framework of opportunity for this.

During January and February 2019, the State Research Agency carried out its first gender equality diagnosis, focused on the Agency's funding activities, by collecting quantitative and qualitative data.

The design followed by the Strategic Group in this I Gender Equality Plan is aimed at identifying needs and implementing measures to promote effective equality between women and men in R&D&I funding activities, which is the main mission of the AEI. This is without prejudice to the actions regarding personnel and the internal structure of the Agency, foreseen in the successive Equality Plans between women and men in the General State Administration and its public bodies.

The Agency has approached gender equality actions from the conviction that its actions, criteria, and rules can have a positive impact, directly or indirectly, on:

- >> Reducing the situation of inequality and under-representation of women in leadership, visibility, recognition, and presence in positions of high responsibility in the R&D&I system, especially significant in some scientific-technical areas.
- >> Palliating the consequences of possible interruptions in the research activity of those women, especially young women, who may have been disproportionately affected by maternity and care, as well as the right to work-life balance for all, through - among other measures - the proper assessment of periods for calculating curricular merits in calls for proposals and other requirements associated with them.
- >> Promoting a balanced presence of men and women in decision-making bodies and processes related to the evaluation and funding of R&D&I activities.
- >> Promoting a more inclusive content with respect to the gender perspective in scientific and technical proposals through the incorporation of sex and gender variables, strengthening the evaluation and monitoring processes of the projects.

- >> Promoting the careers of women researchers by supporting the balanced presence of women in all activities derived from their research activity, including leadership as PIs of research projects, or their participation in evaluation bodies and processes.
- >> Consolidating an organisational culture in the R&D&I system that is sensitive to gender equality and intolerant of discrimination and harassment based on gender, identity, or gender orientation.

2.- AREAS OF ACTION

Gender equality action areas indicate broad areas of an organisation's activity where the problems or shortcomings detected in an institution can be framed, and therefore serve to guide both the diagnoses themselves and the equality measures to be implemented. The SUPERA project already foresaw some general areas of action for funding agencies to guide the initial diagnosis on the gender impact of funding activities.

Based on the results of the diagnosis and the participatory sessions of the Strategic Group on Gender Equality (GEI-AEI), but also on the specialised literature, the previous experience of other contexts in the European Research Area (ERA), and the experience accumulated through measures previously implemented in its activities and calls for proposals, the Agency has defined five main areas of action in terms of equality that would correspond to the nature and capacity for action of a state funding agency of these characteristics:

The areas of action included in this document refer to the R&D&I funding activities carried out by the AEI and will be complemented and coordinated with the objectives and measures of the AEI's Gender Equality Plan, framed within the 3rd Gender Equality Plan of the General State Administration (AGE), currently being drawn up.

3.- PRIOR WORK ON EQUALITY

The State Research Agency has been developing different actions in the field of gender equality for years. This I Gender Equality Plan aims to integrate them coherently, together with other new ones, in a structured work that achieves a greater impact and makes it possible to evaluate and monitor the results. The actions that the Agency had initiated prior to the design of the I Gender Equality Plan, which will be maintained during its implementation, can be included in the aforementioned areas of action:

1. STRUCTURES AND MECHANISMS FOR GENDER EQUALITY.

>> The Royal Decree 1067/2015 creating the State Research Agency recognises the principle of gender equality, the promotion of the gender perspective in research content and the balanced composition in all bodies and committees of the Agency.

>> The AEI's Annual Action Plans include gender equality among its eight operational principles.

>> The AEI annually compiles and analyses gender-disaggregated data on the outcome of the calls for R&D&I grants it manages.

2. AWARENESS RAISING, TRAINING AND ORGANISATIONAL CULTURE

>> From 2019, the AEI organises an annual training course on gender equality for its entire staff.

>> All recent AEI calls for proposals have been modified for using a more inclusive language that mentions and addresses everyone.

>> The AEI has included a section on "[Science in Equality](#)" on its website, where basic information on gender and science is disseminated and the institution's commitment is made visible.

3. FUNDING ACTIVITIES FOR GENDER STUDIES

>> Since 2009, in the structure of the scientific-technical areas of the AEI, which coordinate the evaluation and scientific management of the AEI's funding activities, there has been a specific sub-area (FEM), within the area of social sciences, for the evaluation and funding of research projects on Feminist, Women's, and Gender Studies, in the field of social sciences.

>> Funding is also envisaged for studies on women and gender, as well as other topics that include a gender perspective, in any of the scientific-technical areas of evaluation and funding of the AEI.

>> The AEI participates in the ERA-NET Cofund "GENDER-NET Plus" to promote the Spanish participation in transnational projects on gender studies.

4. SCIENTIFIC EVALUATION

>> The main calls for proposals include a question on the gender perspective in the content of the research in the application forms, which must be developed in the scientific-technical report of the proposal.

>> All calls for research proposals include, among the evaluation criteria, the evaluation of the gender perspective in the socio-economic impact of the proposals.

>> The experts who participate in the evaluation of proposals are given an information note for the correct evaluation of the gender perspective in the content of the research.

>> In the calls *Severo Ochoa Centres of Excellence* and *María de Maeztu Units*, among the evaluation criteria of the objectives of the strategic plans, the measures planned to promote the integration of sex/gender analysis in the content of the research are evaluated whenever it is relevant to avoid gender bias, when the impact of the results and applications of the research carried out may directly or indirectly affect people. Likewise, in the training and incorporation of human resources, actions aimed at ensuring gender equality in all categories of personnel are valued.

>> All the Agency's calls for proposals incorporate the principle of gender-balanced composition in the technical and evaluation committees. This balanced composition encounters difficulties in those scientific and technical areas with a lower proportion of female researchers.

5. IMPACT ON RESEARCH CAREERS

>> The calls for Human Resources (*Ramón y Cajal* and *Juan de la Cierva*) and R&D&I projects (Generation of knowledge and Challenges) extend the period of eligibility from the date of obtaining the PhD degree during the period referred to, for both women and men, for the birth, adoption or fostering of a child (12 months per child); for temporary incapacity during pregnancy for reasons related to it; for other temporary incapacities; for leave of absence due to childcare, family care, gender violence and terrorist violence; for a reduction in working hours due to legal guardianship, direct care of a family member, or to care for a minor affected by a serious illness; and for care of dependent persons, in accordance with the provisions of Law 39/2006, of 14 December.

>> In calls for R&D&I proposals, the period for calculating curricular merits (usually the last 10 years) is extended in the situations indicated in the previous point.

>> The calls for Human Resources (*Ramón y Cajal, Juan de la Cierva* and pre-doctoral contracts) provide for the interruption of aid in cases of maternity and paternity, adoption, pregnancy, breastfeeding, among others.

>> The call for *Severo Ochoa Centres of Excellence* and *María de Maeztu Units* establishes that the strategic plans must analyse the situation from a gender perspective, and draw up a plan to correct possible imbalances between men and women scientists, in each of the professional categories, both in the incorporation of talent and in training, including quantifiable objectives.

In this call, for the calculation of the requirements for research personnel who can be guarantors, the interruption due to possible maternity or paternity has been considered, allowing that, in the calculation of the 5 years in which the merits are considered, for each child born during this period, one year is substituted for a previous one.

4.- AREAS OF WORK, OBJECTIVES AND MEASURES 2021-2023

Based on the previous work already carried out by the AEI in the field of equality and the needs detected in the diagnosis, for the period 2021-2023 the AEI has prioritised six areas of work corresponding to three fields of action (see Annex I). In each area of work, realistic and specific objectives have been designed with their corresponding measures, which are listed below:

GENDER EQUALITY STRUCTURES AND MECHANISMS

>> **Objective 1:** to improve the analysis, monitoring and dissemination of sex-disaggregated data.

- **Measure 1.1:** to publish, after the main grant award decisions, a report with sex-disaggregated data on funding actions, analysing success indicators, distribution by thematic areas, score profiles, and age, among other indicators.
- **Measure 1.2:** to analyse the application and distribution by sex of the measures to mitigate interruptions in research activity, in the evaluation of curricular merits, and other requirements associated with them.

>> **Objective 2:** to strengthen and consolidate the structures of the AEI in charge of implementing effective equality measures equality between women and men, in a sustained manner over time.

- **Measure 2.1:** to adapt, until the Equality Unit of the AEI is set up, the composition and functions of the GEI-AEI to equality activities: those contemplated in this I Gender Equality Plan for funding activities, and those derived from the AGE Gender Equality Plan,
- **Measure 2.2:** to make progress towards the constitution of an Equality Unit in the AEI, this integrates all activities related to equality.

AWARENESS RAISING, TRAINING AND ORGANISATIONAL CULTURE

>> **Objective 3:** to improve specific training in gender equality, aimed at the scientific-technical management of the AEI's calls for proposals.

- **Measure 3.1:** to provide an annual training course for AEI staff on gender equality in the management of calls for proposals.
- **Measure 3.2:** to design dissemination activities and materials aimed at raising awareness and training panel members of the AEI's thematic areas, technical commissions and evaluators, on gender equality and gender bias in evaluation.

>> **Objective 4:** to promote the improvement of gender mainstreaming in R&D&I projects submitted to AEI calls for proposals.

- **Measure 4.1:** to develop supporting materials for research staff on the integration of a gender perspective in the approach, methodology and expected impact of the project.
- **Measure 4.2:** to analyse research project applications that include and describe, in the application form, the gender perspective of the proposed research.

SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNICAL MONITORING AND EVALUATION

>> **Objective 5:** to coordinate the proper implementation of the equality criteria set out in the regulatory bases.

- **Measure 5.1:** to extend and adapt the application of the gender equality criteria established in the regulatory bases of the different calls for proposals managed by the AEI.
- **Measure 5.2:** to develop more precise instructions for improving gender balance in the selection of face-to-face and remote male and female evaluators.

>> **Objective 6:** To systematically mainstream the gender perspective in the scientific and technical evaluation and monitoring of grants.

- **Measure 6.1:** to include descriptors and sections on gender perspective in the evaluation and monitoring report templates.
- **Measure 6.2:** to design self-training activities on gender mainstreaming for the people who will carry out evaluation and monitoring tasks of the AEI grants.

>> **Objective 7:** to identify possible factors underlying the different success rate of women and men as principal investigators (PIs) of projects.

- **Measure 7.1:** To carry out an analysis, with a gender perspective, of the different success rates of women and men as project PIs in the different thematic areas, in order to identify possible causes and to implement the appropriate corrective measures.

5.- IMPLEMENTATION PLANNING

The Agency's Strategic Group on Gender Equality will be responsible for monitoring the implementation, as well as for reporting back to the Directorate General of the Agency as internally established. The responsibility and deadlines for the execution of each of the measures have been established according to criteria of suitability and optimisation of the organisation's time and resources, as follows:

Measure	Responsible Unit	Resources	Implementation Deadline	Monitoring indicators
1.1. To publish a report with sex-disaggregated data on funding actions after the main grant award decisions, among other indicators.	Support Unit	AEI Staff and Scientific Collaborators	Continuous 2021-2023	- Number of calls for proposals for which a report is available
1.2. To analyse the application and distribution by sex of the measures to mitigate interruptions in research activity.	Programming, Economic and Administrative Management Division	AEI staff	Continuous 2021-2023	- Number and type of authorised measures -Distribution by gender
2.1. To adapt, until the Equality Unit of the AEI is set up, the composition and functions of the GEI-AEI to the equality activities of the AEI: those contemplated in this I Gender Equality Plan for funding activities, and those derived from the AGE Gender Equality Plan.	Directorate General	AEI staff	2021	- New composition and functions of the GEI-AEI
2.2. To make progress towards the constitution of an Equality Unit in the AEI, integrating all equality activities.	Directorate General	AEI staff	2021	- Evidence of progression/steps taken
3.1. To provide an annual training course for AEI staff on gender equality in the management of calls for proposals.	Scientific-technical Coordination, Evaluation and Monitoring Division/ Women and Science Unit MCIN	SUPERA Project	Continuous 2021-2023	- Number of sessions/year - Number of attendees/course Evaluation results presented to the GEI-AEI

3.2. To design dissemination activities and materials aimed at raising awareness and training panel members of AEI's thematic areas, technical commissions and evaluators, on gender equality and gender bias in evaluation.	Scientific-technical Coordination, Evaluation and Monitoring Division / Women and Science Unit MCIN	SUPERA Project	Continuous 2021-2023	- Summary of activities carried out, and materials produced and distributed
4.1. To develop support material for research staff on the integration of a gender perspective in the approach, methodology and expected impact of the project.	Scientific-technical Coordination, Evaluation and Monitoring Division / Women and Science Unit MCIN	SUPERA Project	Continuous 2021-2023	- Number of calls for proposals incorporating the Briefing Note on Evaluating the Integration of Gender Analysis in Research (Women and Science Unit) and other materials for applicants/total
4.2. To analyse research project applications that state and describe, in the application form, the gender perspective of the proposed research.	Programming, Economic and Administrative Management Division	AEI staff	Continuous 2021-2023	- % of applications stating and describing the gender perspective in the proposal
5.1. To extend and adapt the application of the gender criteria established in the regulatory bases to the different calls for proposals managed by the AEI.	Programming, Economic and Administrative Management Division	AEI staff	Continuous 2021-2023	- Number of calls for proposals that include all gender criteria/total
5.2. To develop more precise indications for improving gender balance in the selection of evaluators.	Scientific-technical Coordination, Evaluation and Monitoring Division	AEI staff	Continuous 2021-2023	- % of female evaluators by scientific area
6.1. To include descriptors and sections on gender perspective in the evaluation and monitoring report templates.	Scientific-technical Coordination, Evaluation and Monitoring Division	AEI staff	Continuous 2021-2023	- Agreed gender descriptors - List of gender-sensitive evaluation and monitoring report templates

<p>6.2. To design self-training activities on gender mainstreaming for people who will carry out evaluation and monitoring tasks of the AEI's grants.</p>	<p>Scientific-technical Coordination, Evaluation and Monitoring Division / Women and Science Unit MCIN</p>	<p>SUPERA Project</p>	<p>Continuous 2021-2023</p>	<p>-Number of persons who carry out self-training activities before participating as experts.</p>
<p>7.1. To carry out an analysis, with a gender perspective, of the different success rates of women and men as project PIs in order to identify possible causes and to implement the appropriate corrective measures.</p>	<p>Scientific-technical Coordination, Evaluation and Monitoring Division</p>	<p>AEI staff</p>	<p>2021</p>	<p>- Analysis report on the different success rate of women and men as project PIs, and recommendations presented to the GEI-AEI and the Equality Unit of MICIN.</p>

In 2023, the Strategic Group, in collaboration with the future Equality Unit of the Agency, will carry out an independent evaluation of the impact of the measures adopted in the I Gender Equality Plan, as well as other additional that have been carried out during the implementation period. The results of this evaluation will incorporate recommendations for the maintenance or modification of the measures and objectives adopted in the I Gender Equality Plan for the design of the II Plan.

The AEI, through the Strategic Group on Gender Equality, will collaborate with the Equality Unit, the Women and Science Unit of the MCIN, and the SUPERA project in the implementation of the measures included in this I Gender Equality Plan, by virtue of the Agreement signed on 27/11/2019, which articulates the management entrustment for the performance of the functions attributed to the Equality Units by RD 259/2019 regulating the Equality Units of the General State Administration.